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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL ANTI-LICE SHAMPOO FROM *PONGAMIA PINNATA* LEAVES

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Abstract:

This study focuses on the formulation of an herbal anti-lice shampoo for paediatric use, utilizing petroleum ether extract of Pongamia pinnata leaves.

The extract demonstrated strong pediculicidal and ovicidal activity against Pediculus humanus capitis, addressing the growing concern of drug resistance in head lice treatment. Pongamia pinnata contains various bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, polyphenols, alkaloids, and saponins, which contribute to its therapeutic properties. By using herbal antilice shampoo in place of synthetic nitilice shampoo, the emergence of resistance shown by lice against shampoo can be reduced.

The collected leaves were dried using hot air oven, followed by extraction using petroleum ether with soxhlation process. The soxhlation was done for 4 hr. at 40°C. Resulting extract was then concentrated using rotary evaporator. The concentrated extract was incorporated into a shampoo formulation containing glycerine, sodium benzoate, cocoamidopropyl betaine, ethylene glycol monostearate, essential oils, and other mild surfactants to enhance efficacy and stability.

The shampoo was evaluated for color, odour, texture, pH, viscosity, and stability, dirt dispersion, cleaning action, pediculocidal and ovicidal activity. The results indicate that the formulation effectively eliminates lice by enhancing the penetration and bioavailability of active oil components. This study highlights the potential of herbal alternatives in paediatric lice treatment while ensuring reduced toxicity and irritation compared to conventional chemical-based shampoos.

Key words: Pongamia pinnata, shampoo, pediculocidal, ovicidal, stigmasterol

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INTRODUCTION:

Pongamia pinnata, a well-known and widely grown species in the Fabaceae family, has numerous medicinal values from leaves, roots, seeds, flowers, and fruits. The tree is also known by the name Karanja.

It is used in indigenous medicine as digestive, laxative, anthelmintic, it is also used to treat diarrhoea, leprosy, dyspepsia, and cough. The *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil is used effectively against rheumatism. The roots of the plant used to clean teeth, treat ulcers, strengthen gums, and treat gonorrhoea. The flowers of the plant are used in treating diabetes Dipsea, also Vata and Kapa imbalances. *Pongamia pinnata* extracts contains antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, and can help maintain the balance between pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines.

The extract contains a variety of phytochemicals like: flavonoids, polyphenols, alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, phenols, glycosides, carbohydrates, and fixed oils. The pediculocidal activity is shown by the presence of stigmasterol. The antilice property of *Pongamia pinnata* is discussed in the Korean J Parasitol journal. [1]

The prevalence of resistance of lice towards synthetic antilice shampoos is increasing day by day. The introduction of herbal antilice shampoo can counteract this disadvantage. [2]

The petroleum ether extract prepared by soxhlation method followed by rotary evaporation was used to prepare the shampoo. The extract was found to show great pediculocidal and ovicidal activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection and Authentication of plant

Fig.1 *Pongamia pinnata*

fig.2 fresh leaves

fig.3 dried leaves

The leaves were collected from a tree of *Pongamia pinnata* in a rural area of Thrissur during the month of early October 2024. The leaves of *Pongamia pinnata* was authenticated by Dr. Rogimon P. Thomas, Ph.D. Associate Professor & Head Department of Botany, CMS College Kottayam (Autonomous), Kerala, India

Extraction Method

The collected *Pongamia pinnata* leaves were thoroughly washed with water and dried using hot air oven at 60° c until they reached a powdery consistency.

Extraction of *Pongamia pinnata* was done by Soxhlet extraction method petroleum ether was used as the Menstruum. Weighed about 20g of powdered sample and prepared a thimble using filter paper. Soxhlet extractor is connected to the flask containing the petroleum ether as menstruum. The temperature was set to 40°c and solvent was allowed to boil. Solvent evaporate over the distillation arm and flood into the chamber housing thimble. The soxhlation process is done for 4 hours. After the soxhlation process the product obtained is collected and kept in rotary evaporator to remove the petroleum ether and pure extract is collected

Fig.4 soxhlation process

fig.5 rotary evaporator

Fig. 6 extract

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

I. Organoleptic Evaluation]

- Colour
- Texture
- Odour

II. Phytochemical tests [3 - 5]

The presence of various phytochemicals were tested in the extract of *Pongamia pinnata*. Tests were done for the presence of:

Alkaloids

1. Dragendorff's Test:
1 ml of Dragendorff's reagent was added to 2 ml of the filtrate along the side of the test tube. Formation of orange or orange reddish brown precipitate indicated positive result.
2. Mayer's Test:
Mayer's reagent added to 1 ml of filtrate along the sides of the test tube. A white or a creamy precipitate confirmed the positive test.
3. Wagner's Test:
2 ml of plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Iodine-potassium iodide, also called Wagner's reagent was added to this. Formation of a brownish red colour indicates the presence of alkaloid in extract.

Flavonoids

1. Shinoda Test :
Ninety-five percent ethanol was used to dissolve the extract test solution. Three to five drops of the concentrated HCl were added to this, along with a tiny bit of magnesium foil metal. Deep cherry red color formed. Suggests the presence of flavonoids
2. Lead acetate Test:
2 ml of plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Add 1-2 ml of Lead acetate solution to it and mix. Formation of yellow or white precipitate. Indicates flavonoid presence.
3. Alkaline Reagent Test:

2 ml of plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Add 1-2 mL of 10% sodium hydroxide solution to the extract. Formation of a yellow, orange or red color Indicates presence of flavonoids

Sterols

1. Liebermann-Burchard Test
2ml of plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Add 1-2 mL of acetic anhydride and 1-2 mL of sulphuric acid to the extract. Formation of a green or blue colour suggests the presence of sterol
2. Salkowski Test
2ml of plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Add 1-2 mL of chloroform and 1-2 mL of sulphuric acid to the extract. Formation of a red or pink color Indicates sterol presence.
3. Roth-Barton Test:
2ml plant extract was taken in a test-tube. Add 2ml of chloroform and 2ml of potassium dichromate to it and mixed. Formation of green or blue colour indicates the presence of sterol.

Tannins

1. Potassium Dichromate Test (K₂Cr₂O₇ Test):
Mix 1-2 mL of plant extract with 1-2 mL of potassium dichromate and 1-2 mL of sulphuric acid. Orange-red or brown color Indicates presence of tannins.
2. Gelatine Test:
1-2 mL of plant extract was taken in test-tube. 1-2 mL of gelatine and 1-2 mL of HCL was added and mixed. Precipitation of tannin-gelatine complex Indicates presence of tannins
3. Ferric Chloride Test (FeCl₃ Test):
Mix 1-2 mL of plant extract with 1-2 mL of ferric chloride and 1-2 mL of HCL. Greenish black colour present Indicates presence of tannins

Saponin

1. Foam Test (Saponin Test):
Mix 1-2 mL of plant extract with 5-10 mL of distilled water. Shake vigorously for 1-2 minutes. No foam formed. This indicates absence of saponins
2. Sodium carbonate test:
Add a drop of Na₂CO₃ solution to 5 mL of extract in a test tube, shake vigorously, and let it rest for five minutes. No foam formation Indicates absence of saponins
3. Lead acetate test:
Treat 1mL of plant extract with 1% lead acetate solution. No foam formation was found. It indicates absence of saponins

III. Determination of maximum wavelength and calibration curve for petroleum ether extract using UV- visible spectroscopy [6]

Method: UV Visible spectroscopy was used to determine the maximum wavelength of pongamia pinnata extract. The stock solution of pongamia pinnata extract was made with concentration 1 mg/ml in petroleum ether. Using the stock solution different concentrations of extract (10, 20, 30, 40 mg/ml) were made in petroleum ether using dilution method. The absorption spectrum was then read by spectrophotometer in the range of 200-800nm for all dilution and determine the lambda max of pongamia pinnata extract. At this maximum wavelength, the calibration curve of pongamia pinnata extract was drawn and linear equator. The extract in petroleum ether was calculated in the obtained diagram.

IV. Thin layer chromatography [7]

Thin layer chromatography is a form of solid/ liquid chromatography where a thin layer of solid powder held uniformly on a glass plate form a stationary phase and Mobile phase runs over spreading the compounds of the mixture. After developing plates are viewed under normal and UV light to visualize departed compound otherwise use detection reagents.

Thin layer chromatography is based on the principle of adsorption chromatography or

Partition chromatography depending upon the adsorbent. The compound with more affinity towards stationary phase travels slower and the compound with less affinity towards the stationary phase travels faster.

Procedure:

- Prepare the developing container: The developing container for TLC can be designed a chamber with a lid/ breaker with a watch glass .Pour the mobile phase into the chamber. The mobile phase used Hexane:

Acetone by the ratio of 8:2 then cover it with a lid.

- Prepare TLC plate: Plate are prepared by mixing the absorbent such as silica gel with small amount of binding agents like distilled water(30 gm./60 ml) form a homogeneous mixture . By using a pouring method, pour the slurry into the glass slide and make it a thin layer. The substrate is put into an oven and the temperature is controlled at 100°C, 30 minutes drying time after that cooled at room temperature.
- Spot the TLC plate: The crude extract leaves was applied 1 cm above from the lower edge of plate along with the reference of standard compound stigmasterol. Then the plate was developed in an airtight container containing a mobile phase. After the plate were developed it will allow for air dry then sprayed Anisaldehyde sulphuric reagent (Mix 0.5 ml anisaldehyde with 10 ml glacial acetic acid, then add 85 ml ethanol, and finally add 5 ml concentrated sulphuric acid) and heated. Which showed the spots which harmonized with that of the reference standard.

The RF value of standard stigmasterol (0.47 ±0.02).

The marked spots are scrapped and collected.

V. FTIR analysis [6]

Fourier transform spectroscopy differs from conventional (dispersive) spectroscopy in that all of the resolution elements or wavelength intervals for a spectrum are measure simultaneously. In infrared spectroscopy, when IR radiation is passed through the sample. Some of the infrared radiation is absorbed by the sample and some of it is passed through (transmitted).

VI. DPPH Assay [8]

The free radical scavenging activity of the sample was evaluated by assessing its ability to scavenge DPPH radicals. A DPPH reagent solution was prepared by mixing 100 µl of DPPH (1 mm) with 100 µl of methanol (98%). Test solutions were prepared by adding varying volumes of the sample (T1=20 µl, T2=40 µl, T3=60 µl, T4=80 µl, T5=100 µl) to the DPPH reagent solution, adjusting the final volume to 300 µl. A control sample was prepared using solvent, and ascorbic acid served as the standard. After 30 minutes of incubation in the dark at room temperature, the absorbance was recorded at 515 nm. Antioxidant activity.

Radical Scavenging Assay: control od-test OD/ control OD 100

FORMULATION OF SHAMPOO

(Table.1- formulation of shampoo)

Ingredients	Quantity in percentage (%)	Working formula(g)
Plant extract	20	20
Glycerine	12	12
Aloe Vera	5	5
Cocamino propyl betaine	30	30
Ethylene glycol monostearate	4	4
Cocomono	10	10
Methyl cellulose	0.6	0.6
Gum acacia	5	5
Sodium benzoate	1.5	1.5
Distilled water	8	8
Essential oil	q.s	q.s
Cocodi	q.s	q.s
Citric acid	q.s	q.s

Method of preparation:

In a beaker containing glycerine (12%) and CAPB (Coco amino propyl betaine) (30%), heated to 70 degree, Add melted EGMS (4%). To another beaker, containing water (8%), and aloe gel (5%) heated to 70 degree. Add melted cocomono (10%). To the second mixture, add preservative sodium benzoate (1.5%), gum acacia (5%), methyl cellulose (0.6 %), and mix well. Mix these two mixtures by stirring and avoid foam formation. Add the plant extract (20%, 10%, 5%) mixed with lemon juice. Mix well. Coco di/CDEA is added to increase thickness. PH is corrected by citric acid (pH 5.5). Rose oil/lavender oil added for aroma. For certain evaluations, shampoos with extract concentration of 20%, 10%, and 5% was prepared.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL ANTI-LICE SHAMPOO**I. Organoleptic evaluation: [9]**

Colour, odour and foam producing ability.

II. PH: [10]

PH range determined by using pH meter, to check neutral or slightly alkaline.

III. Dirt dispersion: [11]

Two drops of shampoo added in large test tube contain 10 ml of distilled water. 1 drop of India ink was added the test tube was stoppered and shakes it 10 times. The amount of ink in the foam was estimated and classified as None, Light, Moderate, or Heavy. Shampoos concentrated the ink in the water portion ensures their satisfactory cleaning ability and actual effectiveness

IV. Cleaning action: [9]

The cleaning ability is measured using a wool yarn grease removal test. The wool yarn was weighed properly and 0.5 g grease is mixed with the wool yarn. After that it was placed in 200 ml water containing 1 gram of shampoo in a Stoppered flask. Temperature of water was maintained at 35°C. The flask was shanked for 4 minutes at the rate of 50 times a minute. The solution was removed and sample was taken out, then washed with clear water, dried and weighed. The amount of grease removed was calculated.

V. Foaming ability and foam stability: [12]

25 ml of the 1% shampoo solution put into a 100 ml graduated measuring cylinder and covered with hand and shaken for 10 times. The foam volume was calculated. Immediately after shaking the volume of foam were recorded. The stability of foam generated by formulated shampoo for 2 minutes show that foam has good stability. Foamability of prepared shampoo containing 5 %, 10 % and 20% of plant extract was compared with 3 different shampoos available in market. Standard 1: baby shampoo, standard 2: dheedhi, standard 3: medimix. 25 ml of 1 % solution of each shampoo was taken in 100 ml volumetric cylinder. Shaken for 10 times. And observed.

Foam stability test: After shaking, the shampoo was kept for 30 minute and difference in foam height was observed

VI. Stability studies [9]

Stability study is a critical assessment conducted to evaluate the reliability and shelf life of the product
Relative humidity: 70 %± 5° Temperature: 30°C± 2°C
an artificial humidity chamber was prepared and humidity checked by using a psychometric chart.
Procedure: In to the artificial Humidity chamber,

shampoos of different concentrations (5%, 10%, 20%) and standard were kept along with a beaker of water. And the changes were monitored in different time periods such as (Day 1, 10, 20 and 30).

VII. Invitro diffusion test : [13]

The In Vitro release of *Pongamia pinnata* from the shampoo through egg membrane was studied using modified apparatus. The dissolution medium used was freshly prepared phosphate buffer 5.5. Egg membrane previously soaked overnight in the dissolution medium, was tied to one end of a specifically designed glass cylinder (open at both end). 1 ml of shampoo formulation was kept in donor compartments. The cylinder attached to the stand was suspended in 200 ml of dissolution medium maintained at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The membrane was just touching the receptor medium surface. The dissolution medium was stirred 100 rpm speed using Teflon coated magnetic bead. Each of 10 ml volume were withdrawn periodically at predetermined time interval of 5, 10, 15, 20 min the receptor by an equal volume of the receptor medium and analysed by volumetric method

VIII. Anti-lice activity/pediculocidal activity [1]

To study the pediculocidal activity of shampoo in different concentration, 1% solution of each test sample was prepared along with a blank and a standard shampoo. 1% shampoo was prepared by taking 1ml of shampoo in standard flask and making up to 100 ml by using distilled water. Lice were collected carefully and stored in a closed container along with some hair shafts. Test shampoos of 5%, 10%, 20% concentrations, a standard shampoo used for babies, and a blank of distilled water was taken. 5 ml of the diluted shampoos were poured to a tissue paper bed prepared in a petridish. 6 lice were kept carefully in

each petridish and covered with a watch glass. Same procedure was done for a blank with 5 ml distilled water and standard baby shampoo. The number of lice being dead was observed by the lack of movement and reflex in every 5 minutes. And confirmed by using a light microscope.

IX. Ovicidal activity [1]

A 1 ml solution of diluted shampoo was applied to filter paper in a Petri dish and incubated in a dark room for 14 days. To maintain moisture, 0.1 ml of distilled water was added every 2 days. The hatching of lice eggs was monitored under a microscope, and the percentage of egg emergence was recorded.

X. Selection of best formula

XI. Viscosity test of best formula [14]

Viscosity of a liquid shampoo is determined by using a ATAGO viscometer, diluted shampoo is taken in a beaker and the spindle is dipped in it for about 5 minutes then the reading is taken.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Pongamia pinnata leaves extract underwent the following evaluation parameters.

I. Organoleptic Evaluation

- Colour – yellowish green Colour
- Texture –less viscous
- Odour – a peculiar smell

II. Phytochemical tests

(Table.2- Phytochemical tests)

Test for :	Test	Observation	Inference
Alkaloids	Mayer's test Dragen-Dorff's Test Wagner's Test	Formation of a creamy white precipitate (fig.7) Formation of an orange or red precipitate (fig.8) Formation of a brownish red colour Fig.7 Fig.8	Indicates the presence of alkaloid in extract.

Flavonoids	Shinoda Test Lead acetate Test Alkaline Reagent Test	Deep cherry red colour formed.(fig.9) Formation of yellow or white precipitate (fig.10) Formation of a yellow, orange or red colour Fig.9 Fig.10	Suggests the presence of flavonoids
Sterols	Liebermann-Burchard Test Salkowski Test Roth-Barton Test	Formation of a green or blue colour (fig.11) Formation of a red or pink colour (fig.12) Formation of green or blue colour Fig.11 Fig.12	Suggests the presence of sterol
Tannins	Gelatine Test Ferric Chloride Test (FeCl ₃ Test) Potassium Dichromate Test (K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ Test)	Precipitation of tannin-gelatine complex Greenish black colour present Orange-red or brown colour (fig.13) Fig.13	Indicates presence of tannins
Saponin	Foam Test (Saponin Test) Sodium carbonate test Lead acetate test	No foam formed (fig.14) No foam formation (fig.15) No foam formation was found Fig.14 fig.15	Indicates absence of saponin

III. Determination of maximum wavelength and calibration curve for petroleum ether extract using UV- visible spectroscopy

Fig.16 UV spectroscopy analysis

Conclusions

The UV spectroscopy analysis of petroleum ether extract of *pongamia pinnata* showed maximum absorption peak at 205 nm. Based on the uv spectrophotometric data of the *pongamia pinnata* extract of different concentration in PBS solution demonstrated that the calibrated curve obtained was a straight line and the linear equation was found to be $y=0.0034x-0.0135$ and the R^2 value was 0.99923

IV. Thin layer chromatography

Fig.17 TLC plate

TLC was employed to identify stigmasterol present in petroleum ether extract of *pongamia pinnate*. The retention factor obtained from the sample approximately matches the RF of stigmasterol standard, confirming its presence in the extract.

Distance travelled by solute = 5.3 , Distance travelled by solvent front = 2.6
RF value = $2.6/5.3 = 0.490$

V. FTIR of petroleum ether extract of *pongamia pinnata*

Fig.18 FTIR of extract
(Table 3 – FTIR study of extract)

Sl.no.	Observed frequency	Nature of vibration	Frequency range	Inference
1	3236	O-H vibration	3200-3400	Presence of alcohol (OH) group in the sample where the hydroxyl group is involved in hydrogen bonding
2	2921	Aliphatic stretching CH-	2850-2960	Indicate the presence of saturated hydrocarbon in sample
3	1631	C=Stretching Vibration	1620-1680	The indicate presence of an alkene functional group
4	1216	CO stretching/CH bending	600-1500	The frequency specifically related to C-O stretching of OH group /CH bending of methyl/methylene group

VI. DPPH Assay

Fig.19 DPPH assay

fig. 20 % scavenging graph

(Table 4 – DPPH assay of extract)

Sl no	Sample name	Sample dose (µl)	Absorbance	Sample blank	Corrected OD	Radical scavenging activity %
1	T1	20	1.532	0.539	0.993	5.338
2	T2	40	1.530	0.563	0.967	7.807
3	T3	60	1.527	0.597	0.930	11.344
4	T4	80	1.508	0.604	0.904	13.823
5	T5	100	1.483	0.625	0.858	18.208
6	Control	0	1.049			
7	Standard=100µl		0.081			92.278

Conclusion: The petroleum ether extract of *Pongamia pinnata* (SL 2) demonstrated low antioxidant activity in the DPPH radical scavenging assay, with radical scavenging activities below 50% at all tested concentrations. Consequently, the IC₅₀ value could not be determined.

EVALUATION OF ANTILICE SHAMPOO

I. Organoleptic evaluation

Colour: olive green

Odour: characteristic odour

Texture: smooth and slippery

II. PH Test

Fig.21 PH of shampoo
(Table 5- PH value)

Sl.no.	Formulation code	Value obtained using PH meter
1	5%	5.34
2	10%	5.31
3	20%	5.56
4	Standard shampoo	4.22

Conclusion:

Normal PH range of cosmetic product used in hair is 4.5 - 5.5. The PH of herbal Antilice shampoo was found to be 5.5. Hence it was found to suitable for application on paediatric skin.

III. Dirt dispersion test

Fig.22 dirt dispersion test

Conclusion: The result demonstrated that all formulations (F1, F2, and F3) and standard shampoo exhibit similar cleaning performance. These finding indicate that no dirt remains in the foam, confirming that both the prepared and marketed formulations are satisfactory.

IV. Cleaning action test

Fig.23 yarn before grease removal

Fig.24 yarn after grease removal

Weight of yarn = 1.32 g

Weight of grease = 0.5 g

Weight of yarn + grease = 1.82 g

(Table 6- cleaning action comparison)

Sl. No.	Formulation cord	Weight of dried yarn	Amount of grease removed
1	5%	1.39 g	0.35 g
2	10%	1.45 g	0.29 g
3	20%	1.45 g	0.29 g
4	Standard shampoo	1.64 g	0.10 g

Conclusion: The cleaning action studies revealed that the 5% formulated shampoo exhibit superior and comparable cleaning efficacy compared to other formulation.

V. Foamability and foam stability test

Fig.25 solutions before shaking

Fig.26 solutions after shaking

Fig.27 solutions 30min after shaking

(Table 7 – foam ability and foam stability comparison)

Sl.no.	Sample	Foam height (ml)	Foam power	Foam height after 30 min(ml)	Difference in foam height (ml)
1	Standard 1: Baby shampoo	45	20	43	2
2	Standard 2: Dheedhi shampoo	70	45	67	3
3	Standard 3: Medimix shampoo	50	25	48	2
4	Test 1: 5% shampoo	48	23	45	3
5	Test 2: 10% shampoo	48	23	45	3
6	Test 3: 20 % shampoo	46	21	43	3

Foamability test:

Volume of 1% shampoo solution taken in each volumetric cylinder (initial sample height) = 25 ml

Foam power = foam height - initial sample height

Inference: The foaming nature of all 3 test shampoo was found comparable with two of the standard mild shampoos. Hence the test shampoos are showing great foaming ability.

Foam stability test:

Difference in foam height = initial foam height - final foam height

Inference: All the test shampoos are showing great foam stability and are comparable with that of standards.

VI.Stability study

Stability study is a critical conducted to evaluate reliability and shelf-life of the product. Relative humidity 70%=5°C temperature 30°C=2°C. Using Artificial Humidity chamber. We took a container with a lid and setup a fan inside the container by using DC battery, motor and small plastic fan or propeller blade, to make a small fan model and closed it. After 20 minutes open the container, then to measure the temperature inside and outside the container by using thermometer. Finally adjust the humidity at 70% by using psychometric chart.

Fig.28 artificial humidity chamber

Fig.29 psychometric chart

In psychometric chart contains Dew point and wet point. To measure the temperatures of outside T (Dry bulb T) and inside (wet bulb T). These two points intersected into Wet point 28 and Dry point 34. The Relative humidity of corresponding point to these values was observed as 70%.

Conclusion: There was no physico-chemical damage or deterioration was observed. Stability and acceptability of organoleptic properties (odour and color) of formulations during the storage period indicated that they are chemically and physically stable and there is no fungal growth are observed.

VII. Invitro Analysis

Fig.30 invitro analysis

fig. 31 drug release chart

(Table 8 – invitro analysis comparison)

SL.N O	FORMULATION CODE	TIME(min)	ABSORBANC E	CONCENTRATI ON	% CUMULATIVE DRUG RELEASE
1	5%	5	0.01	3.980	16.8
		10	0.0983	4.068	17.7
		15	0.0994	4.069	18.5
		20	0.1106	4.08	19.5
2	10%	5	0.0196	3.990	15
		10	0.0410	4.011	17
		15	0.0617	4.030	19.2
		20	0.0639	4.034	20.1
3	20%	5	0.0210	3.991	15.2
		10	0.0628	4.033	24.4
		15	0.0905	4.061	30.3
		20	0.1247	4.095	33.2
4	STANDARD	5	0.0103	3.980	13.4
		10	0.0173	3.987	14
		15	0.0273	3.997	15.7
		20	0.075	4.045	16.2

Conclusion: The invitro drug release shows minimal release and 20% formulation provides significant Sustained release. The Analysis conclude that gradual release profile ensure the drug remains on the scalp Surface, allowing for localized therapeutic action.

VIII. Pediculocidal activity

Fig.32 Test (5%)

fig.33 Test (10%)

Fig.34 Test (20%)

Fig.35 Standard (baby shampoo) min Observation

Fig.36 Blank/control

Fig.37 observation after 20 min

(Table 9 – pediculocidal activity study)

Sample	Dead in 0 min	after 5 min	after 10 min	after 15 min	after 20 min
F1	0	0	0	1	2
F2	0	0	1	2	3
F3	0	1	2	5	6
Blank (water)	0	0	0	0	0
Standard(baby shampoo)	0	0	0	0	0

Fig.38 microscopic view of a dead lice

Conclusion

20% shampoo showed great pediculocidal activity. All the specimens kept in this sample were found dead. Hence we can conclude that shampoo having 20% pongamia pinnata extract shows great pediculocidal activity.

IX. Ovicidal activity

The Ovicidal activity was tested 6 brownish egg on a filter paper placed in the bottom of each petridish. Then 1 ml of test shampoo was diluted with 50 ml of water from these 10 ml of each test solution and control was applied on the nits. All the dishes were incubated under a dark camper. After 14 days hatching was monitored.

Ovicidal activity = unhatched in treatment groups / total nits in treatment group \times 100

(Table 10 – ovicidal activity study)

SI NO	Sample	Ovicidal activity after 14 days
1	5%	100%
2	10%	100%
3	20%	100%
4	Standard	0%
5	Control	0 %

Fig.39 ovicidal activity

Conclusion

The results indicate that all shampoo formulation exhibited strong Ovicidal Activity, all treated nits were found dead. In contrast, the control group showed high hatchability, confirming the absence of Ovicidal effects. Hence we can conclude the shampoo prepared from pongamia pinnata leaves extract shows Strong Ovicidal activity.

X. SELECTION OF BEST FORMULA

(Table 11- selection of best formula)

TEST	OBSERVATION	5%	10%	20%
Organoleptic Study	Color Odor Texture	Greenish white Characteristic smooth & viscous	olive green Characteristic smooth & viscous	olive green Characteristic smooth & viscous
PH	By PH meter	5.34	5.31	5.56
Dirt dispersion	Ink in water portion	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Satisfactory
Cleaning action	Amount of grease removed	0.35	0.29	0.29
Foam ability	Foam power	23	23	21
Foam stability	Difference in foam height	3	3	3
Stability study	fungal growth and chemical and physical stability problems	Absent	Absent	Absent

Invitro study	Maximum release in 20 min	19.5	20.1	33.2
Pediculocidal activity	No. of Dead lice in 20 min	2	3	6
Ovicidal activity	Ovicidal activity after 14 days	33	50	100

Hence we can conclude that 20 % shampoo is the best formula for herbal anti-lice shampoo

XI. Viscosity test

Fig.40 viscosity test

fig. 41 : viscosity of test and standard

Viscosity of formulated shampoo was found to be: 9599.2 cP

Viscosity of standard shampoo was found to be: 1142.6 cP

Conclusion

Normal viscosity range of shampoo is 500 – 10,000 cP

The viscosity of test shampoo was found to be within the normal limit

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The study successfully formulated and evaluated a petroleum ether extract of *Pongamia pinnata*-based shampoo with potential anti-lice properties. The shampoo formulation follows an emulsion-based approach, incorporating various harmless chemicals. The materials used ensure that the shampoo remains free from harsh ingredients such as sulfates (SLS) and parabens, making it a safer alternative for hair care. The formulation and evaluation of the extract-based shampoo were successfully conducted. All the evaluation parameters conducted were found to be within the standard range, confirming the reliability and effectiveness of the formulation.

The pediatric herbal anti-lice shampoo developed in this study effectively combats head lice. The formulation done by avoiding harsh chemicals and thus increases the safety of the product. This innovation promotes the decreased reliance on synthetic compounds.

Future researches can be done by refining the formula and can also explore opportunities for commercialization after confirming skin and eye irritation test

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